

γ -Aminobutyrate (GABA) Regulated Defense Tolerance: Mechanisms and Opportunities

Barry J. Shelp^a, Morteza Soleimani Aghdam^b, Edward J. Flaherty^a

^a Department of Plant Agriculture, University of Guelph, Guelph, ON N1G 2W1, Canada

^b Department of Horticultural Science, Imam Khomeini International University, Qazvin, 34148-96818, Iran.

Supplementary Table S1. Important *Arabidopsis thaliana* genes associated with GABA metabolism and signaling.

Gene name	Common gene name	Gene I.D.
<i>ALDH10A8 (AMADH2)</i>	Aminoaldehyde dehydrogenase/4-aminobutanal dehydrogenase	At1g74920
<i>ALDH10A9 (AMADH1)</i>	Aminoaldehyde dehydrogenase/4-aminobutanal dehydrogenase	At3g48170
<i>ALMT1</i>	Aluminum-activated malate transporter	At1G08430
<i>ALMT4</i>	Aluminum-activated malate transporter	At1g25480
<i>ALMT6</i>	Aluminum-activated malate transporter	At2G17470
<i>ALMT9</i>	Aluminum-activated malate transporter	At3G18440
<i>ALMT12</i>	Aluminum-activated malate transporter	At4g17970
<i>CAT9</i>	Cationic amino acid transporter	At1g05940
<i>CuAOα1</i>	Copper amine oxidase	At1g31670
<i>CuAOα3</i>	Copper amine oxidase	At1g31710
<i>CuAOδ</i>	Copper amine oxidase	At4g12290
<i>CuAOζ</i> (previously <i>CuAO3</i> or <i>CuAO1</i>)	Copper amine oxidase	At2g42490
<i>CuAOα3</i> (previously <i>CuAO2</i>)	Copper amine oxidase	At1g31710
<i>DIT1</i>	Dicarboxylate transporter	At5g12860
<i>DIT2.1</i>	Dicarboxylate transporter	At5g64290
<i>DIT2.2</i> ,	Dicarboxylate transporter	At5g64280
<i>DTC</i>	Dicarboxylate-tricarboxylate transporter	At5G19760
<i>GABA-TOG</i>	2-Oxoglutarate-dependent GABA transaminase	uncertain
<i>GABA-TP</i> ,	Pyruvate-dependent GABA transaminase	At3g22200
<i>GABP/BAT1</i> ,	GABA permease	At2g01170
<i>GAD1</i>	Glutamate decarboxylase	At5g17330
<i>GAD2</i>	Glutamate decarboxylase	At1g65960
<i>GAD4</i>	Glutamate decarboxylase	At2g02010
<i>GAT1</i>	GABA transporter	At1g15040

<i>GLYR1/SSR1</i>	Glyoxylate/succinic semialdehyde reductase	At3g25530
<i>GLYR2/SSR2</i>	Glyoxylate/succinic semialdehyde reductase	At1g17650
<i>GORK</i>	Guard cell outward rectifying channel	At5g37600
<i>OMT</i> (mitochondrial)	2-oxoglutarate/malate transporter	uncertain
<i>PAO2,</i>	Polyamine oxidase	At2g43020
<i>PAO3</i>	Polyamine oxidase	At3g59050
<i>PAO4</i>	Polyamine oxidase	At1g65840
<i>PROT1</i>	Proline transporter	At2g39890
<i>PROT2</i>	Proline transporter	At3g55740
<i>PROT3</i>	Proline transporter	At2g36590
<i>SSADH (ALDH5F1)</i>	Succinic semialdehyde dehydrogenase	At1g79440
<i>UCP1</i>	Uncoupling protein	At3g5411
<i>UCP2</i>	Uncoupling protein	At5g58970

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Supplementary Figures.

Tissue	Growth Stage	Age (days)	Notes	
1. Cotyledon	12. Shoot apex, inflorescence	0.1	3	Seed imbibition
2. Rosette leaf 2	13. Root	1.0	6	Cotyledon fully opened
3. Rosette leaf 4	14. Flower stage 12	1.04	17	4 rosette leaves are greater than 1 mm in length
4. Rosette leaf 6	15. Flower stage 12, sepal	1.09	21	9 rosette leaves are greater than 1 mm in length
5. Rosette leaf 8	16. Flower stage 12, petal	1.1	22	10 rosette leaves are greater than 1 mm in length
6. Rosette leaf 10	17. Flower stage 12, stamen	1.12	23	12 rosette leaves are greater than 1 mm in length
7. Rosette leaf 12	18. Flower stage 12, carpel	6.1	36	10% flowers to be produced are open
8. Leaf 7 petiole	19. Mature pollen	6.5	44	50% flowers to be produced are open
9. Hypocotyl	20. Seed stage 4 w/ silique	9.7		Senescence is complete
10. Entire rosette after transitioning to flowering	21. Seed stage 7 w/o silique			
11. Senescing rosette	22. Seed stage 9 w/o silique			
	23. Seed			

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4. Rosette leaf 6	15. Flower stage 12, sepal	1.09	21
5. Rosette leaf 8	16. Flower stage 12, petal	1.1	22
6. Rosette leaf 10	17. Flower stage 12, stamen	1.12	23
7. Rosette leaf 12	18. Flower stage 12, carpel	6.1	36
8. Leaf 7 petiole	19. Mature pollen	6.5	44
9. Hypocotyl	20. Seed stage 4 w/ silique	9.7	
10. Entire rosette after transitioning to flowering	21. Seed stage 7 w/o silique		
11. Senescing rosette	22. Seed stage 9 w/o silique		
	23. Seed		

+	Legend
	0
	6.5
	13
	19.5
	26
	32.5
	39
	45.5
	52
	58.5
	>65

Supplementary Fig. S1. Expression of genes in *Arabidopsis* at select tissue and developmental stages. The heat maps are based absolute expression values as indicated in the colour legend directly below the figure. Expression data were accessed from the AtGenExpression- Tissue Series dataset organized on the Bio-Array Resource for Arabidopsis Functional Genomics (<http://bar.utoronto.ca/>) (Toufighi et al. 2005). Description of growing conditions and developmental stages are described in Schmid et al. (2005).

Supplementary Fig. S2. Relative expression of genes in *Arabidopsis* seedlings exposed to various abiotic stresses.

Absolute expression levels in treated tissue are corrected for levels in control tissues subjected to similar conditions, and the difference expressed as fold-increase (not a ratio) compared to the zero-time control. The heat map is based on log₂-transformed ratios, which can be thought of as two to the exponent of the given value, as indicated in the colour key. Expression data were accessed from the abiotic stress series microarray data set organized on the Bio-Array Resource for Arabidopsis Functional Genomics (<http://bar.utoronto.ca/>) (Toufighi et al. 2005). Plants were grown in tissue culture for 10 days under a typical light–dark regime and the stresses applied as follows: cold, continuously at 4 °C in the presence of control light; drought, 15 min dry air stream and 10% decline in fresh mass followed by recovery; heat, 3 h at 38 °C, followed by recovery; osmotic, 300 mM mannitol in medium; salt, 150 mM NaCl in medium; UV-B, 15 min exposure followed by recovery; wounding, punctured with pins followed by recovery (Kilian et al. 2007).

Abbreviations: *UCP1*, uncoupling protein 1; *UCP2*, uncoupling protein 2, *DTC*, dicarboxylic/tricarboxylic acid transporter; *DIT1*, dicarboxylate transporter 1; *DIT2.1*, dicarboxylate transporter 2.1; *DIT2.2*, dicarboxylate transporter 2.2; *ALMT1*, aluminum-activated malate transporter 1; *ALMT6*, aluminum-activated malate transporter 6; *ALMT9*, aluminum-activated malate transporter 9; *ALMT12*, aluminum-activated malate transporter 12; *CAT9*, cationic amino acid transporter 9; *GAT*, glutamine amido-transferase; *PROT1*, proline transporter 1; *PROT2*, proline transporter 2; *PROT3*, proline transporter 3.

UCP1 (AT3G54110)

At3g54110 251902_at ATPUMPT

UCP2 (AT5G58970)

At5g58970 247746_at ATUCP2

DTC (AT5G19760)

At5g19760.245939_at

DIT1 (AT5G12860)

At5g12860 250278_at DIT1

DIT2.1 (AT5G64290)

At5g64290 247289_at DCT

DIT2.2 (AT5G64280)

At5g64280 247286_at DIT2.2

ALMT1 (AT1G08430)

At1g08430 257481_at

ALMT6 (AT2G17470)

At2g17470 257409_at

ALMT9 (AT3G18440)

At3g18440 257719_at

ALMT12 (AT4G17970)

At4g17970 254697_at

CAT9 (AT1G05940)

At1g05940 260927_at CAT9

GAT1 (AT1G15040)

At1g15040 260741_at

PROT1 (AT2G39890)

At2g39890 267358_at Prot1

PROT2 (At3g55740)

At3g55740 251752_at Prot2

PROT3 (AT2G36590)

At2g36590 263918_at Prot3

Supplementary Fig. S3. Absolute tissue-specific expression of genes in *Arabidopsis* plants exposed to hypoxia. Data were accessed from the dataset organized on <http://efp.ucr.edu/> (Mustrup et al. 2009). Plant material was collected from whole roots, the root tip (apical 1 cm) and the aerial region of 7-day-old *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Col-0) expressing FLAG-RPL18 under the control of regional and cell-specific promoters. Seedlings were grown under 16 h ~80 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ / 8 h darkness at 23 °C on 0.43% MS media containing 1% sucrose. Seedlings were untreated (control) or deprived of O₂ for 2 h by transfer to chambers purged of air with argon (hypoxia).